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Report on **Milestone 14**

Inventory of existing (meta-)data format interoperability solutions

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Abstract:

This report concerns the achievement of Milestone 14 of the SSHOC project. Building on D3.1, this text reports on the process and results of the inventory of existing metadata and data format conversions solutions and describes the architecture of the Interoperability Hub.

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1. Introduction

This document reports on the SSHOC project Milestone 14 inventory process and results. Earlier work of task 3.5 delivered D3.1 *Report on SSHOC (meta)data interoperability problems*¹, which provided an inventory of metadata and data formats used by the SSHOC communities, recommendations for metadata standards and data file formats, and priorities for providing conversion services. MS14 report provides an inventory of existing metadata and data format conversion solutions, technology and practices relevant to the social sciences and humanities per D3.1. These conversion solutions will provide the content for the SSHOC Interoperability Hub and are a starting point for better interoperability. Limitation of scope to (meta)data conversions is explained in D3.1.

When investigating (meta)data conversion solutions, the team has identified two groups of solutions:

1. A ready to use web-service that is provided by a research infrastructure, research center or organisation, or a commercial company;

¹ D3.1 Report in SSHOC (meta)data interoperability problems available on Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/record/3569868#.X4RdeXgzZTY>

2. Complex solutions that can entail the use of several services and manual steps. In the remainder of this report, this type of solutions are referred to as conversion recipes that need to be well-documented.

The sources used in the inventory process were D3.1, re-analysis of the expert interviews conducted in spring 2019, desk research to collect information about existing solutions, and different available SSH service registries and other information sources, e.g. TAPoR², CLAPOP³, CLARIN VLO⁴, PARTHENOS SSK⁵, and DDI Tools⁶.

2. Description of the Milestone

MS14 is available as an internal Google spreadsheet⁷ and a screenshot is included in Appendix A.

EXISTING CONVERSION SERVICES

There are different kinds of conversion services around. The most common ones are tools that have the option to save/export data or to import it from a different file format. Spreadsheet applications are a good example of this: many researchers use such software as well as the potential to export data in a format such as CSV. Such implicit conversion services are dependent on the distribution of a software. Thus, they push the use of selected file formats, whereas formats not supported need to rely on tailored conversion services.

Having a way to convert data from a widely used file format to an adjusted one depends strongly on the usability and the degree of adoption of a tool in a research community. It is important to highlight that common file formats (such as CSV) are useful for sharing data but limit the applications that build upon them. It should also be kept in mind that some file formats are not agnostic to the logic that the data expresses. The different types of file formats and how they are structured also affect if and how data between two formats can be converted.

One important observation here is that conversions for specialised file formats in the SSH domain sometimes rely only on hand-crafted scripts. Coding effort would be necessary to safeguard such formats by creating standardised conversion paths to more common file formats. On the other hand, an active community around tools implies in most cases the existence of conversion services created by this community. Strong indicators for the availability of reliable and up-to-date conversion services are information about last updates of tools

² <http://tapor.ca/home> TAPoR; tools for sophisticated text analysis and retrieval [10.10.2020]

³ <http://dev.clarin.nl> service registry of the Dutch CARIN community [10.10.2020]

⁴ <http://vlo.clarin.eu> the resource catalogue of the CLARIN infrastructure [10.10.2020]

⁵ <http://ssk.huma-num.fr/#/> the PARTHENOS Standards Survival Kit [10.10.2020]

⁶ <https://ddialliance.org/resources/tools> the DDI Alliance's tools list [10.10.2020]

⁷ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1jih3hYrebzF1GMyLoak7Y99tthtI3Hz39BQV-NJPxj4/edit?usp=sharing> MS14 inventory spreadsheet is available within the SSHOC Shared Drive Repository maintained by the project coordinator during the duration of the project implementation [10.10.2020]

or information about the active usage of a format in a research community. Such information is also important due to the frequent need to build up a chain of conversion services to get from one format to another.

The inventory and the attributes about the conversion solutions give a solid basis for instructions on how to find a conversion path. Every solution included in the inventory is described with a number of attributes (spreadsheet columns) that are as often as possible from existing published schema, mostly schema.org⁸ and mapped to SSHOCro⁹. This will form the basis of the data model for the interoperability (conversion) solutions. See Appendix B for the attributes used in this first version of the inventory.

A chain service like the SSHOC Switchboard provides support in building up conversion paths and managing adaptations in-between, e.g. if a conversion service does not exist or is broken.

RECIPES AND COMPLEX CONVERSIONS

Not all known and available conversions can be presented in the form of a desktop installable tool or a web-service. Sometimes conversions require the use of multiple tools and specific manual actions such as the use of an XML editor to inspect the content. These complex conversions may be seen as recipes that need human interpretation and are written in prose text. Such descriptions can be directly provided on the landing page but should also be accompanied (perhaps in-line) with suitable metadata. These types of conversions can be found on the web in manuals, best-practice recommendations, research documents etc. It is important to realise that such sources are often not stable and may disappear at any moment. Some points to remember when implementing this type of conversion solution:

- Complex conversions recipes may be not exact and are not machine-interpretable; they require some contextualisation from the user.
- As with the other type of conversion solutions, a good metadata description should be provided.
- To ensure sustainability (and citability), copying and storing the conversion recipe descriptions should be expedited. This can be arranged in Drupal, but copyright issues need to be addressed.
- Are PIDs needed for citability?
- The development of a specific template for recipes with metadata is part of the workplan for the coming months.

GAP ANALYSIS

⁸ <https://schema.org/> schema.org [10.10.2020]

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3744925> SSHOCro; [10.10.2020]

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/12hCkgSkneySzb5mlKE7DdZr8e3u6WRDD5WmWVItGUu8/edit?usp=sharing> mapping to SSHOCro/PEM is available within the SSHOC Shared Drive Repository maintained by the project coordinator during the duration of the project implementation [10.10.2020]

The priorities for conversion services were outlined in D3.1 and the highest priority was given to SSHOC cross-community solutions as well as conversions needed for the SSHOC Marketplace. Below, the priorities from D3.1 are compared with the inventory of solutions (Appendix A) and gaps outlined.

SSHOC Marketplace and cross-community: A high-priority need is to have the interoperability solutions data model (i.e. service metadata) compatible with the SSHOC Marketplace. For cross-community purposes and especially for discovery, conversions or mappings between the recommended metadata standards (D3.1, Table 6) are a priority. Based on discussions among SSHOC partners, there is also a need for solutions between standards used in the SSHOC communities and standards used in related communities not directly involved with SSHOC, such as archaeology or agriculture. In addition, we will need to discuss further with Task 3.3 which services they need for converting structured data to text format, and with WP9 about interoperability from the perspective of thematic and (inter)disciplinary user communities.

It is also worth noting that not a negligible amount of research information is encoded in default office formats like Word documents or Excel spreadsheets. Even though the generic representation in XML (DOCX, XLSX) is available out of the box, more elaborate, bespoke and/or customizable conversions to community standards are often desirable. In this respect, especially semantic interoperability presents a major challenge.

CESSDA/ESS/SHARE: Within the social sciences, the de facto community metadata standards are DDI Codebook and DDI Lifecycle. Although there are solutions for conversing between these two, and between the DDI formats and general metadata formats like DataCite, they are usually purpose-specific and/or not maintained. There is thus a need to update existing solutions based on SSHOC use case(s). It has also appeared that WP9.2 needs to convert DDI Codebook XML files into a human readable format (for example, html). No general solution that would cover all DDI Codebook elements exists and is probably not needed but this is an aspect not covered in D3.1 nor in the inventory. For data format conversions, there are several available solutions, typically commercial or specific scripts. This is an area where recipes are the best approach for SSHOC.

CLARIN: Within linguistics, the challenges are linguistic annotation format conversions, document and media conversions and CMDI conversions. One of these are already planned to be addressed in task 3.5 as the DDI / CMDI conversion. With respect to conversions that would also be interesting for a more general group, CLARIN is interested in better quality PDF to TEI conversion possibilities or even general PDF to HTML such as ABBYY FineReader, GROBID or TEXTTRACT. The named examples could be added to the second conversion services overview.

DARIAH: As RI for arts and humanities, DARIAH aims to cover a very broad disciplinary spectrum, with traditionally very heterogeneous data landscape/ecosystem, combined with a huge set of applications (in varying maturity stages) to process the data. This yields a large, sparse conversion matrix that is difficult to oversee. As one de-facto for annotated text, TEI is a candidate for a lead format, from which paths to other formats need to be evaluated and established. TEI schema encompassing also the metadata in the <teiHeader> is a source for conversions to various metadata formats. Another relevant data type is bibliographies, but here conversions between various bibliographic formats should be readily available in the general market. Though

images and/or various 3D representations also comprise a substantial part of the humanities data, here only sourcing from existing conversion paths also seems feasible.

E-RIHS: Based on D3.1, the challenge within E-RIHS is metadata conversions. X3ML toolkit includes existing mappings, for example, to CIDOC CRM. Further work is needed to analyse possible gaps from SSHOC viewpoint.

2.1. Role of the Milestone

Work on this milestone has laid ground for further work in task 3.5 for developing the Interoperability Hub and the conversions solutions that will be provided from key SSHOC infrastructure components such as the SSHOC switchboard from T3.6, and should be advertised via the SSHOC marketplace (WP7) and the partner infrastructure registries and catalogues. Therefore suitable (metadata) harvesting interfaces (e.g. OAI-PMH) must be supported. It is expected that the data model (conversion services metadata) can also be an example for similar work in other research domains. If conditions are suitable, it should be possible to also consider opening the Interoperability Hub for other (cross-domain) projects.

Awaiting a more detailed development of SSHOC sustainability plans for services, the team will consider the Interoperability Hub portal as the main deliverable of Task 3.5, essential to be maintained in the future. Appendix C shows the architecture for the Interoperability Hub.

2.2. Means of verification

According to the GA Table 1.3.4 WT4 List of milestones, MS14 provides an inventory of existing metadata or data format interoperability solutions. These interoperability solutions will be the building blocks of the Interoperability Hub. This report provides choices, based on SSHOC recommended formats (as defined in D3.1), that are essential for making SSHOC services interoperable and cloud-ready. The inventory spreadsheet is provided in Appendix A and as an online version (Google spreadsheet) internally accessible to Consortium members.

3. Conclusions and next steps

This Milestone charts progress made in T3.5 after D3.1, providing a common understanding on the Interoperability Hub and further information for selecting solutions to be included in it. Somewhat contrary to expectations, the team did not find many readily available conversion services or solutions. However, there is an abundance of mappings and the valuable mappings need to be sufficiently described and made sustainable.

The goal is to have a data-driven website for the Interoperability Hub, tagged and searchable and including editorial facilities to curate and extend the information. The Interoperability Hub will be one of the tools listed in the SSHOC Marketplace. In addition, the Marketplace will include separate entries of solutions within the Interoperability Hub (see Appendix C).

Next steps will include:

- Finalising the data model for interoperability solutions and normalize the services overview accordingly for inclusion in the Interoperability Hub portal.
- Defining a template for 'recipes' i.e. the descriptions of more complex (multi-tool/service/locally deployed source code) workflows.
- Providing Interoperability Hub portal using the same technological solution as the SSHOC training toolkit: Drupal 8 and Drupal 8's ecosystem Search API.
- Planning and organising both technical maintenance (Drupal) and content maintenance (the descriptions).
- Analysing the gaps in conversion services offerings further; pending on resources available (both PMs and expertise), prioritise either describing solutions or developing new solutions.
- Making the final selection of new solutions to be developed by T3.5, depending on the gaps, the priorities, and on the resources the partners have available.

Further consultation with the SSHOC community is needed and can lead to an extension of the inventory of solutions. MS14 is available as a Google spreadsheet for feedback from the SSHOC community and task 3.5 maintains a working, live version of the inventory spreadsheet with an eye for future extensions.

4. Appendixes

Appendix A. Screenshot of the conversion solution inventory spreadsheet (MS14)

Appendix B. Data model for interoperability solutions

Appendix C. Architecture for Interoperability Hub

Appendix A. Screenshot of the conversion solution inventory spreadsheet (MS14)

Online version in SSHOC Shared Drive Repository :

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1jih3hYrebzF1GMyLoak7Y99thtIT3Hz39BQV-NJPxj4/edit?usp=sharing>

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
SSHOC MS14 v1.0 2020-06-30. Solutions listed in alphabetical order.												
https://schema.org/name	https://schema.org/url	https://schema.org/audience				https://schema.org/license				https://schema.org/creativeWorkStatus	https://schema.org/datePublished	https://schema.org/htmlDate
	URL	which research community uses this (primarily); CLARIN, DARIAH, cross-community, CESSDA, LIBER, ERIHS, NLP	how can the service be used/called	indicates if the service or source code is open and reusable		either name of a well known public license, link to a software license and/or copyright statement	https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.html	https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.html		production, draft, retired, obsolete, in development, as is	ISO 8601 Date, see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_8601	ISO https://en.wikipedia.org
Name of solution	Link to landing/info page	community	invocation type	free/commercial	open/proprietary	Terms of Use/License	input format	output format	Status of the solution	Maturity	Publication Date	Mc
3M	Landing page: https://isi.ics.forth.gr/3M info page: https://www.ics.forth.gr/isi/x3ml-toolkit	cross-community	web application, local deployments are possible	open	open	Licensed under the EURL, Version 1.1 or - as soon they will be approved by the European Commission - subsequent versions of the EURL: http://ec.europa.eu/idabc/eurl	xml	rdf triples compliant to a target schema.e.g CIDOC CRM/PEM/CERIF, SSHOCro	maintained	production		
Audacity	https://www.audacityteam.org/	cross-community	local tool	free	open	GPL2	audio data (multiple formats)	audio data (multiple formats)	maintained	production	?	
Beautiful Soup	https://www.crummy.com/software/BeautifulSoup/	cross-community	library ; web application	free (LaunchPad)	open	MIT	websites (screen scraping)	text, code structure	maintained	production		2004
CHAMD	https://github.com/UUDigital-Humanities/lab/chamd	CLARIN	code	open	open	https://github.com/UUDigital-Humanities/lab/chamd/blob/develop/LICENSE	CHAT	PaQu metadata (https://dev.clarin.nl/node/14366)	maintained			2018
CMDI2DC	http://weblicht.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/converter/CMDI2DC/	CLARIN	RESTful webservice	free	https://github.com/SFS-ASCL/CMDI2 open	https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT	CMDI according to some specified profiles	Dublin Core (XML)	maintained	production		2017-01-19
CMDI2Marc21	http://weblicht.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/converter/CMDI2Marc/	CLARIN	RESTful webservice	free	https://github.com/SFS-ASCL/CMDI2 open	https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT	CMDI according to some specified profiles	MARC21 (XML)	maintained	production		2017-01-19
CMDI2RDF	https://github.com/clarin-eric/CMDI2RDF	CLARIN	source-code / webservice	open	open	GPL v3	CMDI	RDF	maintained?	production		2014
Colectica for Excel	https://www.colectica.com/software/collecticaforexcel/	CESSDA	UI	commercial	proprietary	https://www.colectica.com/legal/eula/	SAS, Stata, SPSS	xlsx	maintained	production		
DDI Converter	https://git.oesis.org/standat/standat-converter	CESSDA				http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0	DDI Codebook	DDI Lifecycle 3.2	in development	in development		
DDI to HTML Stylesheet	http://www.ddialliance.org/system/files/codebook2-0.xsl	CESSDA	code	open	open	See comment in http://www.ddialliance.org/system/files/codebook2-0.xsl	DDI Codebook 2.0	html	no longer developed but still available	as is		2004-06-01
EAF recipe	https://tla.mpi.nl/topic/converting-clan-files-to-elan-files/	CLARIN	INFO	open	open	http://ec.europa.eu/idabc/eurl	CHAT	EAF	not maintained	as is		2013 -
ELAN	https://archive.mpi.nl/tla/elan	CLARIN, DARIAH,	local tool	open	open	GPL v3	many import/export options ao. CSV, TextGrid, CHAT	many import/export options ao. CSV, TextGrid, CHAT	maintained	production		2006
epidoc-xslt	https://github.com/DCLP/epidoc-xslt/	CLARIN	scripts	free (GitHub)	open	GPL v3.0	EpiDoc XML	text formats e.g. TEI	finished	production		2014
Handbrake	https://handbrake.fr/	cross-community	local tool	free (GitHub)	open	GPL2 & BSD3	video data (multiple formats)	video data (multiple formats)	maintained	production	?	
HowTo ACDH-CH: Mapping scenario	https://howto.acdh-oeaw.ac.at/blog/mapping-mysql-database-to-rdf-with-karma/	cross-community	INFO	free	open	CC BY-SA 4.0	SQL-DB	RDF	finalized	draft		2017
Imagemagick	https://imagemagick.org/index.php	cross-community	library/local tool	open	open	http://imagemagick.org/script/license.php	image formats	image formats	maintained	production		<2011
jq	https://stedolan.github.io/jq/	cross-community	command line tool ; webservice	free (GitHub)	open	MIT	JSON	CSV	maintained	production		< 2013
Karma	https://usc-isi-2.github.io/karma/	cross-community	webservice	free (GitHub)	open	Apache 2.0	CSV, SQL-DB	RDF	maintained	production		2016?
Kuha2	https://kuha2.readthedocs.io/en/latest/	CESSDA	API	open	open	https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/custom-page/attachment/2020-03/EUPL-1.2%20EN.pdf	DDI-C 1.2.2, DDI-C 2.5, DDI-L 3.1, API available for format independent input bibliographic records (MARC) - see https://librecat.org/Catmandu/#importers	EAD3, Dublin Core, DDI2.5	maintained	production		2017-10-25
LibreCat & Catmandu	https://librecat.org/index.html	LIBER	web application	free (GitHub)	open	GPL v2.0		JSON, XML	maintained	production		2013
Metadata Transform PDI-XSL T	https://github.com/MetadataTransform/pdi-xslt	CESSDA	code	open	open	GNU / GPL	DDI Lifecycle 3.1 (and 3.2)	MARC, DDI Codebook 1.2.2, DataCite 2.2, rdf, XHTML	Need approx 2 weeks work to solve known bugs and to update to 3.3			2013/2014

4	Name of solution	Link to landing/info page	community	invocation type	free/commercial	open/proprietary	Terms of Use/License	input format	output format	Status of the solution	Maturity	Publication Date	Mc
26	Nominatim	https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Nominatim	cross-community	web application (API)	free (GitHub)	open	GPL v2.0	Text on geographic data like address, name of city	OSM Geocoordinates	maintained	production	< 2013	
27	OpenConvert	http://openconvert.clarin.nl/openconvert/web/help.html	CLARIN, DARIAH	UI, INFO	open	open		text, html, alto, word, docx, epub	tei, folia,	maintained	production	2015	
28	OpenRefine	https://openrefine.org/	cross-community	local tool	free (GitHub)	open	BSD-3	various (meta)data	various (meta)data	maintained	production	2000s?	
29	PanDoc	https://pandoc.org	CLARIN, DARIAH	UI, local tool, code	open	open	GPL v2	csv, various	tei, various	maintained	production	2008	
30	Pepper	https://corpus-tools.org/pepper/	CLARIN	local tool (java)	free (GitHub)	open	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/	linguistic data (ELAN, EXMARaLDA, Praat, PAULA, TigerXML, ANNIS, ...)	linguistic data (see input format)	maintained	production	2010s?	
31	Piereling	https://pypl.org/project/piereling/	CLARIN	code, API service	open	open	GNU General Public License v3 (GPLv3)	Folia, various	Folia, others	maintained	production	2019	
32	Praat	http://www.fon.hum.uva.nl/praat/manual/TextGrid_file_formats.html	CLARIN, DARIAH	local tool, command processor	open	open	GPL v2	TextGrid/bin	text			1995	
33	QGIS	https://www.qgis.org/en/site/	DARIAH, CESSDA, ERIHS	local tool	free (GitHub)	open	GPL v2.0	geocoordinates e.g. shapefiles	csv	maintained	production	?	
34	R script with 'haven' package	https://haven.tidyverse.org/	CESSDA	code	open	open	https://haven.tidyverse.org/LICENSE.html	SPSS (.sav, .por), SAS (.sas7bdat, .sas7bcat, SAS Xport), Stata	SPSS (.sav), Stata (.dta)	maintained		2015-03-04	
35	REFI	www.qdasoftware.org	cross community,	NA	commercial	open							a data exchange standard, (to be) implemented in ATLAS.tI, Dedoose, Hanalyse, MAXQDA, NVivo, QDAMiner, Quirkos and Transan
36	Sledgehammer	https://ddialliance.org/tools/sledgehammer	CESSDA	UI, can be run programmatically	freeware			Stata, SPSS, SAS, DDI+ASCII, StatTransfer+ASCII,SQL	ASCII text format (fixed, csv, delimited) + generating scripts for reading ASCII data into R, SAS, SPSS, Stata, Mathematica Notebook, Berkeley SDA, and various flavors of SQL	abandoned	retired/obsolete (no longer available)	v1.0 2015-07-17 (latest v	
37	Smallpdf	https://smallpdf.com/	cross-community	web application	commercial (free trial for 14 days)	proprietary	unclear	PDF, PPT, JPG, DOCX, DOC	PDF, PPT, JPG, DOCX, DOC	maintained	production	?	
38	Spreadsheet software like MS Excel, LibreOffice Calc, GoogleSpreadsheet	https://www.libreoffice.org/ ; https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-365/excel	cross-community	local tool	free ; commercial	open ; proprietary	Mozilla Public License v2.0 / Microsoft copyright license	manual created data ; spreadsheet formats (CSV, ODS, XLS, XLSX, ...)	spreadsheet formats (CSV, ODS, XLS, XLSX, ...), PDF	maintained	production	?	
39	SSK Scenario: Corpus Modelling	http://sks.huma-num.fr/#scenarios/SSK_scenario_corpusModellinginTEI	CLARIN	INFO	free (GitHub)	open	CC BY 4.0	Various Text	TEI	finalized	production	2017	
40	StatTransfer	https://stattransfer.com/	CESSDA	UI, command processor	commercial	proprietary	https://stattransfer.com/ordering/prices/	multiple, for example ASCII, DDI, R, SAS, SPSS, Stata, Statistica, Triple-S	multiple, for example ASCII, DDI, R, SAS, SPSS, Stata, Statistica, Triple-S	maintained	production	1986	
41	Tabula	https://tabula.technology/	cross-community	local tool	free (GitHub)	open	MIT	Tables in PDF	CSV, XLS, XLSX	maintained	production	2013	
42	TEI-OxGarage	https://oxgarage2.tei-c.org	CLARIN	webservice	free (GitHub)	open	GPL v3	Documents (TEI, DOC, DOCX, ODT, TXT, RTF, ...), Presentations (PPT, PPTX, ODR, SXI), Spreadsheets (CSV, XLS, XLSX, ODS, SXC, TSV)	Documents (TEI, DOC, DOCX, LaTeX, ePub, RTF, PDF, XML, ...)	maintained	production	2000s?	
43	TEI→TCF encoder+decoder	http://kaskade.dwds.de/tei-tcf/	CLARIN	web application	free	unclear	unclear	TEI/TCF	TEI/TCF	unclear	prototype? (v0.06)	?	?
44	TEIconvert	http://ct3.ortolang.fr/teiconvert/index-en.html	CLARIN	UI	open	open	License CC+BY et BSD 2	TEI, +	TRS/CHA/TEXTGRID/EA/TF/TXT/DOCX/XLSX	?	production		
45	Tesseract OCR	https://tesseract-ocr.github.io/ ; https://github.com/tesseract-ocr/tesseract	cross-community	local tool	free (GitHub)	open	Apache 2.0	images of scans (JPG, GIF, ...)	plain text, hOCR (HTML), PDF, invisible-text-only PDF, TSV, ALTO (XML)	maintained	production	2000s?	
46	WLFxB	https://weblicht.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/weblichtwiki/index.php/Reading_and_writing_TCF#Consuming_and_producing_linguistic_annotations_from_2Finto_TCF	CLARIN, NLP	code, library	free	open		various	tof	maintained	production	2010-07-09	
47	XSLT, XPath, XQuery, XSL-FO	https://www.w3.org/standards/xml/transformations	CLARIN	INFO, standards	free	open?	Copyright	XML	text formats like html, plain text but also formats like pdf	finished	production	?	
48	XSugar	https://www.brics.dk/xsugar/	CLARIN	local tool	free	open?	Copyright	XML/non-XML	non-XML/XML	abandoned	production	2004	

Appendix B. Data model for interoperability solutions

From the inventory we have the following conversion solution attributes (metadata descriptors) and initial vocabularies. The vocabularies will be normalised for integration to the Drupal platform.

Community: which research community uses this (primarily)?

- repeatable term from vocabulary {CLARIN, DARIAH, cross-community, CESSDA, LIBER, ERIHS, NLP}
- Outliers are: NLP and LIBER

Invocation type: how can the service be used/called

- Repeatable term from vocabulary {UI, INFO, local tool, code, API service, library, RESTful web service, source code, command processor, can be run programmatically, local deployments are possible, web application, local tool (java), command line tool, scripts, web application (API) }
- Many can be easily mapped on preferred terms.
- Mapping proposal with definitions
- RESTful web service, API service, web application API -> **server-side web API** : a server side programmatic interface
 - Code -> **source code**
 - Local tool (java), local tool, command processor -> **local tool** : a compiled software that needs to be installed on the user's desktop computer
 - **Library** : compiled source code that provides a programming API
 - **Script** : a machine/OS/tool interpretable series of commands to perform a task
 - **INFO** : a human interpretable description to perform a task or how to invoke specific services to perform a task
 - Web application : is a software or program which is accessible using a web browser
 - **UI** : local tool or web application with a User Interface (note this is mostly a superfluous description since local tools and web applications almost always have a UI)
 - Command line tool -> **Command processor** : a tool/service that has the ability to interpret commands or execute whole scripts.
 - NOTE: "local tool" almost always implies UI even if not specified
 - NOTE "web application" almost always implies also UI

Free/commercial is an unclear term but the attribute is used to indicate if the service or source code was open and reusable

- Non-repeatable term from vocabulary {commercial, open, free, free (GitHub), freeware, commercial (free trial), free (LaunchPad), free; commercial}
- Can be simplified and mapped on preferred terms but the name used for the attribute should be changed and clarified.

Terms of Use / License

- String either name of a well known public license, link to a software license and/or copyright statement
- The open licenses names can be simplified

Input formats

- Repeatabe term from vocabulary {alto, API available for format independent input, ASCII, CHAT, CMDI, csv, DDI, DDI+ASCII, DDI Codebook, DDI-C 1.2.2, DD-C 2.5, DDI-L 3.1, doc, docx, EpiDoc xml, epub, html, image formats, multiple, odt, R, rtf, SAS, SPSS, Stata, Stat/Transfer+ASCII, Statistica, SQL, SQL-DB, TEI, TextGrid, TextGrid/bin, Triple-S, various, various metadata, various text, word,

Output formats

- Repeatabe term from vocabulary { ASCII, Berkeley SDA, CHA, CHAT, csv, DataCite 2.2, DDI, DDI codebook 1.2.2, doc, docx, EAF, ePub, json, LaTeX, Lifecycle 3.2, DDI2.5, Docx, Dublin core (XML), EAD3, EAF, folia, html, image formats, MARC, MARC21 (XML), Mathematica Notebook, PaQu metadata, pdf, rtf, tcf, tei, TRS, various, OSM geocoordinates, others, R, RDF, RDF (CIDOC CRM/PEM/CERIF/SSHOCro scheme compliant), SAS, SPSS, Stata, Statistica, various metadata, various flavours of SQL, TextGrid, Triple-S, xhtml, xml, xslx,

Expected level of knowledge

- Term from vocabulary { advanced, DDI-expert, expert, novice, OAI-PMH expert, R expert }

Maturity

- Term from vocabulary {production, draft, retired, obsolete, in development, as is }

Application category

- Term from vocabulary {data processing, data processing; mapping }

Application sub-category

- Term from vocabulary {conversion }

Appendix C. Architecture for Interoperability Hub

